

Microwave assisted organic reactions in 1-hydroxy carbazole-2-carbaldehyde

Ramya V[#] and Sangeetha V^{*}

PG and Research Department of Chemistry, Kongunadu Arts and Science College, Coimbatore-641029, Tamilnadu, India.

**Department of Chemistry, Kongunadu Arts and Science College, Coimbatore-641029, Tamilnadu, India.*

Abstract

Microwave assisted organic synthesis (MAOS) has emerged as a new “lead” in organic synthesis. The technique offers simple, clean, fast, efficient, and economic for the synthesis of a large number of organic molecules. Conventional method of organic synthesis usually need longer heating time, tedious apparatus setup, which result in higher cost of process and the excessive use of solvents/ reagents lead to environmental pollution. A review of the literature reveals that MAOS has advantage over conventional heating because of its shorter reaction times and formation of cleaner products. The focus of this paper is to summarise some microwave assisted organic reaction employed for the synthesis of variety of hetero annulated cyclopent[*b*]indole and carbazole derivatives with high yield. In this work we made an attempt to prepare some furo carbazole, thiazepino carbazole and quinolino carbazole by microwave assisted method by using 1-hydroxycarbazole-2-carbaldehyde. Where 1-hydroxy carbazole-2-carbaldehyde were irradiated with *o*-aminothiophenol, phenylacetic acid and chloroacetone to give corresponding thiazepino, acetyloxy and acetylfuro carbazole respectively. The synthesised products were purified by column chromatography and analysed by spectral techniques viz., IR, ¹H NMR and mass spectroscopy.

Keywords: *Microwave assisted Conventional method, carbazole, furo carbazole, thiazepino carbazole and quinolino carbazole.*

I INTRODUCTION

In the recent year microwave assisted organic reaction has emerged as new tool in organic synthesis. Important advantage of this technology include highly accelerated rate of the reaction, Reduction in reaction time with an improvement in the yield and quality of the product. Now day’s technique is considered as an important approach toward green chemistry, because this technique is more environmentally friendly. This technology is still under-used in the laboratory and has the potential to have a large impact on the fields of screening, combinatorial chemistry, medicinal chemistry and drug development.

Conventional method of organic synthesis usually need longer heating time, tedious apparatus setup, which result in higher cost of process and the excessive use of solvents/ reagents lead to environmental pollution. This growth of green chemistry holds significant potential for a reduction of the by product, a reduction in waste production and a lowering of

the energy costs. Due to its ability to couple directly with the reaction molecule and by passing thermal conductivity leading to a rapid rise in the temperature, microwave irradiation has been used to improve many organic syntheses. In contemporary age, development of new greener, energy efficient and fast synthesis of heterocyclic fused carbazoles are of substantial interest to organic chemists due to their widespread applicability in organic, biochemical, and pharmacological fields. Rapidly emerging publications of microwave-assisted synthesis encompass almost all sorts of synthetic reactions involved in heterocycles construction. Some researchers also use domestic microwaves, which do not provide a scientifically acceptable reproducibility level. In past, biologically active carbazole alkaloids [1] were chiefly obtained from diverse natural origins. But in present age various classical as well as non-classical methods have been developed to synthesize these significant molecules. By keeping an eye on green chemistry [2] and atom economy, a number of synthetic protocols with mild reaction conditions under microwave irradiations have been explored up till now. Most of these methods are historic to afford carbazoles from good to excellent yields. A review of the literature reveals that MAOS has advantage over conventional heating because of its shorter reaction times and formation of cleaner products. The focus of this paper is to summarise some MW assisted organic reaction employed for the synthesis of variety of hetero annulated cyclopent[*b*]indole and carbazole derivatives with high yield.

In this context section 2 presents the information which is related to micro wave irradiated synthesis of carbazole derivatives. Section 3 gives the details of materials and methods which is used in synthesis. Section 4 discusses the microwave assisted reaction on 1-hydroxy carbazole-2-carbaldehyde. Section 5 discusses the experimental results of 1-hydroxy carbazole-2-carbaldehyde derivatives. Finally section 6 discusses the conclusion and feature studies.

II LITERATURE REVIEW

Microwave irradiated synthesis of carbazole analogues

J.A.Seijas and his co-workers [3] have synthesised 9*H*-Dibenzo[*a,c*]carbazole in basic environment under microwave irradiation. The reaction occurred mechanistically by oxy-Cope rearrangement and Madelung condensation followed by subsequent oxidation. Base catalyzed microwave irradiated cyclization of *N*-acyl-*o*-toluidine derivatives underwent Madelung's reaction to produce 2-phenylindole derivative. Anionic oxy-Cope rearrangement, a [1,3]-sigmatropic as well as oxidation steps led to the final product. Kulkarni, A *et al* [4] reported Microwave assisted Friedel-Crafts alkylation of indole by hexane-2,5-diol as an influential alkylating agent followed by consequential aromatization was explored as an effective method to synthesize highly selective substituted carbazoles. Gomez, M.V and his co-workers [5] had synthesised carbazole analogues by Diels-Alder cycloaddition of nitro indole derivative and different dienophiles under solvent-free and microwave conditions. Saravanabhavan, M. and his co-workers [6] have reported Lewis acid catalyzed intermolecular cyclization reaction for the efficient synthesis of pyrido[2,3-*a*]carbazole *via* one pot reaction. 1-chloro-2-formylcarbazole along with ethanolamine was subjected to microwave irradiation in the presence of *p*-toluenesulfonic acid to afford the desired product. Velmurugan, R and his co-workers [7] have synthesised carbazole based pyrazoles and oxazoles were successfully obtained *via* microwave irradiations. 1-oxo-1,2,3,4-tetrahydrocarbazole and benzaldehyde underwent microwave assisted Aldol condensation to

afford 2-benzylidene-1-oxo-1,2,3,4-tetrahydrocarbazole which was treated with hydroxylamine hydrochloride in ethanol to afford isooxazolocarbazole derivative and with hydrazine hydrate in ethanolic environment to obtain substituted pyrazolocarbazole derivative. Chitra, S. and co-workers [8] have reported Fischer indole reaction under microwave irradiation. In which 2-(3-oxo-1,3-diarylpropyl)-1-cyclohexanone and phenylhydrazine hydrochloride were subjected to Fischer indole reaction in aqueous medium under microwave irradiation. The reaction progressed smoothly to afford 1*H*-pyrido[3,2,1-*jk*]carbazole derivative. Forke, R and co-workers [9] have reported copper catalyzed electrophilic iodination of methyl-2-hydroxy-9*H*-carbazole-3-carboxylate under microwave. The iodinated substrate, in turn, was coupled with indolyl substrate in the presence of palladium catalyst and dioxane solvent.

III MATERIALS AND METHODS

Melting points were determined on a Boetius micro heating table or on a Raga heating block and are uncorrected. Thin Layer Chromatography [TLC] was performed using glass plates coated with silica gel G [incorporating CaSO₄ (13%) as binder]. Petroleum ether and ethyl acetate were used as irrigant. Spots were visualized with iodine. Purification of the crude samples was carried out using chromatographic columns packed with silica gel (60-120 mesh). IR Spectra were recorded on Shimadzu FT IR 8201(PC)S spectrometer model spectrometer, using KBR disc method and the absorption frequencies quoted in reciprocal centimeters (cm⁻¹). ¹H-NMR spectra were taken on BRUKER-400 (400 MHz), BRUKER-500 (500 MHz) spectrometer using trimethylsilane (TMS) as internal reference. The chemical shifts are quoted in parts per million (ppm) (s=singlet; d=doublet; t=triplet; q=quardret; bs=broad singlet and m=multiplet). Elemental analysis was performed on Vario EL III CHNS analyzer and Perkin-Elmer analyzer. Microanalysis was obtained (C, H, N, ± 0.4%). The reactions were carried out in a domestic microwave oven (Godrej-OM20ESP, 2450MHz).

IV EXPERIMENTAL

Microwave assisted organic reactions in 1-hydroxycarbazole-2-carbaldehyde

In this context, we made an attempt to prepare some furo carbazole, thiazepino carbazole and quinolino carbazole by microwave assisted method where utilizing 1-hydroxycarbazole as a potential precursor in our synthetic strategy. In this connection, 1-oxo-1,2,3,4-tetrahydrocarbazole(1) were first reduced to give corresponding 1-hydroxy carbazole(2), which is further treated with zinc cyanide in dry ether to give appropriate 1-hydroxycarbazole-2-carbaldehyde(3) with high yield according to already reported procedure[10].

1-3

a: R₁ = CH₃, R₂ = R₃ = Hb: R₂ = CH₃, R₁ = R₃ = Hc: R₁ = R₂ = R₃ = H

263 and also elemental analysis agreed well with the molecular formula $C_{17}H_{13}NO_2$. A series of similar compounds **5b** and **5c** were obtained from **3b** and **3c** respectively.

Scheme 3

Microwave assisted reaction of 1-hydroxycarbazole-2-carbaldehyde (3a-3c) with phenylacetic acid

1-Hydroxy-6-methyl-carbazole-2-carbaldehyde (**3a**) was irradiated with phenylacetic acid in acetic anhydride at $120^\circ C$ for 15 min. The reaction was monitored for every one minute by using TLC. After completion of the reaction, the crude product was purified by column chromatography yielded 1-acetyloxy-6-methylcarbazole-2-carbaldehyde (**6a**). The structure of **6a** was well established by elemental analysis and spectral data. IR spectrum of **6a** showed strong absorption at 3247 cm^{-1} , 1759 cm^{-1} and 1669 cm^{-1} which are assigned for $-NH$, estercarbonyl and aldehydic carbonyl groups respectively. The 1H NMR spectrum of **6a** showed two singlets at δ 2.13 and δ 2.93 for three protons of C_6-CH_3 and $C_1-OCOCH_3$ respectively. The signals due to indole-NH and C_2-CHO resonated as singlet at δ 8.51 and δ 12.61 respectively. The aromatic cluster appeared at δ 7.27- 8.02 was due to C_3-H , C_4-H , C_5-H , C_7-H and C_8-H protons respectively. The mass spectrum of the compound **6a** showed the molecular ion peak at 325. The elemental analysis was agreement with the molecular formula $C_{16}H_{13}NO_3$. A series of similar compounds **6b** and **6c** were obtained from **3b** and **3c** respectively.

Scheme 4

V RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Microwave assisted reaction of 1-hydroxycarbazole-2-carbaldehyde (3) with *o*-aminothiophenol

General procedure : A mixture of respective 1-hydroxycarbazole-2-carbaldehydes (**3**, 0.001 mol) were irradiated with *o*-aminothiophenol (0.001 mol) in acetic acid (8 ml) for 20 min. The reaction was monitored by TLC for every 1 min. After completion of the reaction, the reaction mixture was poured in to an ice. The obtained product was purified by column chromatography over silica gel using petroleum ether-ethyl acetate (90:10) to yield the corresponding compounds (**4**).

10-methylbenzo[1,2-*b*]-1,4-thiazepino[7,6-*a*]carbazole (4a)

Yellow solid, Yield : 0.179 g (57%); m.p. : 288-290⁰C; IR (KBr cm⁻¹) ν_{\max} : 3415, 1616, 1473, 1477, 1402, 1292; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) [δ ppm] : 2.50 (s, 3H, C₁₀-CH₃), 7.10-7.73 (m, 9H, C₁-H, C₂-H, C₃-H, C₄-H, C₇-H, C₈-H, C₉-H, C₁₁-H and C₁₂-H), 8.35 (s, 1H, C₆-H), 11.64 (s, 1H, indole -NH).

Anal.calcd for C₂₀H₁₄N₂S : C, 76.36 %; H, 4.49 %; N, 8.91 %; Found: C, 76.22 %; H, 4.12 %; N, 8.45 %.

11-methylbenzo[1,2-*b*]-1,4-thiazepino[7,6-*a*]carbazole (4b)

Yellow solid, Yield : 0.187 g (59%); m.p. : 285-287⁰C; IR (KBr cm⁻¹) ν_{\max} : 3328, 1623, 1493, 1477, 1241, 956; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) [δ ppm] : 2.10 (s, 3H, C₁₁-CH₃), 7.12-7.67 (m, 9H, C₁-H, C₂-H, C₃-H, C₄-H, C₇-H, C₈-H, C₉-H, C₁₀-H and C₁₂-H), 8.84 (s, 1H, C₆-H), 10.45 (s, 1H, indole -NH).

Anal.calcd for C₂₀H₁₄N₂S : C, 76.36 %; H, 4.49 %; N, 8.91 %; Found: C, 76.29 %; H, 4.42 %; N, 8.66 %.

Benzo[1,2-*b*]-1,4-thiazepino[7,6-*a*]carbazole (4c)

Yellow solid, Yield : 0.190 g (63%); m.p. : 273-274⁰C; IR (KBr cm⁻¹) ν_{\max} : 3365, 1636, 1521, 1482, 1239, 956; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) [δ ppm] : 7.32-7.90 (m, 10H, C₁-H, C₂-H, C₃-H, C₄-H, C₇-H, C₈-H, C₉-H, C₁₀-H, C₁₁-H and C₁₂-H), 8.32 (s, 1H, C₆-H), 11.20 (s, 1H, indole -NH).

Anal.calcd for C₁₉H₁₂N₂S : C, 75.97 %; H, 4.02 %; N, 9.32 %; Found: C, 76.53 %; H, 4.12 %; N, 9.15 %.

Microwave assisted reaction of 1-hydroxycarbazole-2-carbaldehyde (3) with chloroacetone

General procedure : A mixture of respective 1-hydroxycarbazole-2-carbaldehyde (**3**, 0.001 mol) was irradiated with chloroacetone (0.001 mol) and K₂CO₃ (0.5 g) in acetone (8 ml) for 5 min. The reaction was monitored by TLC for every 30 sec. After completion of the reaction, the reaction mixture was poured in to an ice. The obtained product was purified by column chromatography over silica gel using petroleum ether-ethyl acetate (95:5) to yield the corresponding compound (**5**).

2-acetyl-7-methylfuro[2,3-*a*]carbazole (5a)

White solid, Yield : 0.210 g (80%); m.p. : 240-242⁰C; IR (KBr cm⁻¹) ν_{\max} : 3363, 1660, 1577, 1450, 1369, 1292, 1167, 964; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) [δ ppm] : 2.42 (s, 3H, C₂-COCH₃), 3.05 (s, 3H, C₇-CH₃), 7.07-7.55 (m, 3H, C₆-H, C₈-H and C₉-H), 8.12-8.25 (m, 3H, C₃-H, C₄-H and C₅-H), 11.21 (s, 1H, indole -NH).

Anal.calcd for C₁₇H₁₃NO₂ : C, 77.55 %; H, 4.97 %; N, 5.31 %; Found: C, 77.30 %; H, 4.47 %; N, 5.20%.

2-acetyl-8-methylfuro[2,3-*a*]carbazole (5b)

Dirty white solid, Yield : 0.215 g (81%); m.p. : 229-230⁰C; IR (KBr cm⁻¹) ν_{\max} : 3346, 1658, 1577, 1463, 1369, 1325; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) [δ ppm] : 2.36 (s, 3H, C₇-CH₃), 3.76 (s, 3H, C₂-COCH₃), 6.91-7.43 (m, 3H, C₆-H, C₇-H and C₉-H), 8.05-8.13 (m, 3H, C₃-H, C₄-H and C₅-H), 10.79 (s, 1H, indole -NH).

Anal.calcd for C₁₇H₁₃NO₂ : C, 77.55 %; H, 4.97 %; N, 5.31 %; Found: C, 77.25 %; H, 4.56 %; N, 5.13%.

2-acetylfuro[2,3-*a*]carbazole (5c)

Dirty white solid, Yield : 0.196 g (79%); m.p. : 232-234⁰C; IR (KBr cm⁻¹) ν_{\max} : 3359, 1662, 1620, 1550, 1463, 1325, 1296; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) [δ ppm] : 3.76 (s, 3H, C₂-COCH₃), 6.93-7.47 (m, 4H, C₆-H, C₇-H, C₈-H and C₉-H), 8.11-8.14 (m, 3H, C₃-H, C₄-H and C₅-H), 10.93 (s, 1H, indole -NH).

Anal.calcd for C₁₆H₁₁NO₂ : C, 77.09 %; H, 4.44 %; N, 5.61 %; Found: C, 77.02 %; H, 4.23 %; N, 5.33%.

Microwave assisted reaction of 1-hydroxycarbazole-2-carbaldehyde (3) with phenylacetic acid

General procedure: A mixture of appropriate 1-hydroxycarbazole-2-carbaldehyde (**3**, 0.001 mol) was irradiated with phenylacetic acid (0.001 mol) in acetic anhydride (5 ml) for 15 min. The reaction was monitored by TLC for every 1 min. After completion of the reaction, the reaction mixture was poured in to an ice. The obtained product was purified by column chromatography over silica gel using petroleum ether-ethyl acetate (80:20) used as an eluent.

1-acetyloxy-6-methylcarbazole-2-carbaldehyde (6a)

White solid, Yield : 0.230 g (80%); m.p. : 175-177⁰C; IR (KBr cm⁻¹) ν_{\max} : 3247, 1759, 1666, 1566, 1371, 1292, 1186, 1132, 1017; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) [δ ppm] : 2.13 (s, 3H, C₆-CH₃), 2.93 (s, 3H, C₁-OCOCH₃), 7.27-8.02 (m, 5H, C₃-H, C₄-H, C₅-H, C₇-H and C₈-H), 8.51 (s, 1H, indole -NH), 12.61 (s, 1H, C₂-CHO).

Anal.calcd for C₁₆H₁₃NO₃ : C, 71.89 %; H, 4.90 %; N, 5.24 %; Found: C, 71.19 %; H, 4.67 %; N, 5.13 %.

1-acetyloxy-7-methylcarbazole-2-carbaldehyde (6b)

White solid, Yield : 0.230 g (86%); m.p. : 157-159⁰C; IR (KBr cm⁻¹) ν_{\max} : 3322, 1727, 1617, 1544, 1336, 1276, 1121; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) [δ ppm] : 2.75 (s, 3H, C₇-CH₃), 3.03 (s, 3H, C₁-OCOCH₃), 7.25-7.74 (m, 5H, C₃-H, C₄-H, C₅-H, C₆-H and C₈-H), 8.40 (s, 1H, indole -NH), 11.48 (s, 1H, C₂-CHO).

Anal.calcd for C₁₆H₁₃NO₃ : C, 71.89 %; H, 4.90 %; N, 5.24 %; Found: C, 71.30 %; H, 4.45 % ; N, 5.21 %.

1-acetyloxy-carbazole-2-carbaldehyde (6c)

White solid, Yield : 0.230 g (80%); m.p. : 160-162⁰C; IR (KBr cm⁻¹) ν_{\max} : 3320, 1715, 1617, 1434, 1336, 1249, 1101; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) [δ ppm] : 3.05 (s, 3H, C₁-OCOCH₃), 7.07-7.53 (m, 6H, C₃-H, C₄-H, C₅-H, C₆-H, C₇-H and C₈-H), 8.52 (s, 1H, indole -NH), 8.68 (s, 1H, C₂-CHO).

Anal.calcd for C₁₅H₁₁NO₃ : C, 71.13 %; H, 4.37 %; N, 5.53 %; Found: C, 71.23 %; H, 4.20 % ; N, 5.21 %.

VI CONCLUSION

Carbazole has become leading pharmacophore which continues to receive increasing attention from medicinal chemists due to unique biological properties of indole derived compounds, especially, anticancer activity. Based on our interest to synthesise some hetero annulated compounds containing various heterocyclic rings. In this view this work described in detail about the microwave assisted reaction on cyclopent[*b*]indole and some carbazole derivatives. Where 1-hydroxycarbazole-2-carbaldehyde was irradiated with *o*-amino thiophenol, chloroacetone and phenylacetic acid to give respective product as benzo[1,2-*b*]-1,4-thiazepino[7,6-*a*]carbazoles, 2-acetylfuro[2,3-*a*]carbazoles and 1-acetyloxy-carbazole-2-carbaldehydes in an high yield with shorter reaction period of time. Whereas in conventional method the above said reactions were carried out with longer period of time and the yield is very low which was already reported. In the entire above said microwave assisted reactions we synthesised the respective compounds without any production of by-products.

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